

OPTICAL INACTIVITY OF GELATIN IN THE ADSORBED STATE AT THE LIQUID/LIQUID INTERFACE AND ITS USE AS A MEASURE OF ADSORPTION.

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Optical rotation for transparent emulsions of amyl acetate in gelatin-water-glycerol sols of various concentrations have been found experimentally and compared with those calculated from Beer's law for mixtures. The observed rotations are found to be less than the calculated from which it is inferred that the gelatin particles on being adsorbed on the oil globules become optically inactive.

The optical inactivity of adsorbed gelatin has been used as a measure of its adsorption at the liquid/liquid interface in transparent emulsions as well as such milky emulsions as could be made transparent by the addition of glycerine. From the difference between the calculated and observed values, the values of x/m (quantity of gelatin adsorbed by one g. of the oil) have been calculated and found to be nearly constant for the different quantities of the adsorbent used. The value of x/m increases with the increase in initial concentration.

It has been experimentally proved that the gelatin in the adsorbed state at the liquid/liquid interface loses optical activity only temporarily.

In emulsions the emulsifying agent is said to be adsorbed at the interface of the continuous and the disperse phases in accordance with the Gibbs-Thomson law, that is, it forms an envelope round each oil globule suspended in the dispersion medium.

There has long been a controversy over the protecting nature of this envelope; some take it to be a purely physical phenomenon, while others like Zsigmondy ("The Chemistry of Colloids", 1917, p. 112) and Langmuir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1845) postulate that chemical forces are acting. Bhatnagar and Shrivastava (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 730) have supported the presence of chemical forces between adsorbent and the adsorbed film by showing experimentally that various optically active sugars become inactive when adsorbed on colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, etc. They have utilised this optical inactivity as a measure of adsorption of sugars on the colloidal particles. Holmes and Child (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2049), failed to determine quantitatively any adsorption of gelatin on oil globules in kerosene-in-water emulsions.

The object of the present investigation was to see if the gelatin being an optically active substance, becomes optically inactive on being adsorbed on oil globules in transparent emulsions of amyl acetate in gelatin-glycerol

sols of various concentrations, and whether this inactivity, being the difference between the calculated and observed optical rotations of the emulsions, could be utilised as a measure of its adsorption at the liquid/liquid interface to settle finally the cause of stability of the emulsions containing gelatin as the emulsifying agent.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

It was found from preliminary experiments that transparent and very slightly chromatic emulsions could be prepared by dispersing amyl acetate in a mixture of gelatin-water sol of various concentrations and glycerine, each having a refractive index equal to that of the disperse phase. The gelatin-water sols were prepared as suggested by Sheppard and Houck (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 273). Pure gelatin (Merck's Gold Label) was used.

The proportions of various gelatin-water sols and glycerine in the various continuous phases used, and the optical properties of the latter are described in Table I. The refractive indices were determined by means of Abbe's refractometer whose prisms were enclosed in metal jackets through which water was run from a temperature regulator. The optical rotations were determined by means of half-shade polarimeter fitted with potassium dichromate gel filter and verniers reading to 0.01 degree. The liquid was enclosed in a 100 mm. tube, enclosed in a metal jacket, through which water was run from a temperature regulator; a 200-watt electric bulb was used as a source of light. The refractive index, n_D^{25} for amyl acetate was found to be 1.397, its optical rotation = 0 and its specific gravity ρ at the room temperature (35°) was found to be 0.8619.

TABLE I.

Cont. phase No.	Gelatin sol.	gel-water sol.	Glycerine.	%Gelatin in cont. phase.	n_D .	Rotation optical.	Rotation specific.
1	0.50%	56.50 c.c.	43.50 c.c.	0.2825 g.	1.3970	-0.34	-120.4
2	0.75	56.75	43.25	0.4257	1.3970	-0.51	-119.8
3	1.00	57.00	43.00	0.5700	1.3970	-0.69	-121.1
4	1.50	57.50	42.50	0.8626	1.3970	-1.00	-116.0
5	2.00	58.00	42.00	1.1600	1.3970	-1.37	-118.1
6	2.50	58.50	41.50	1.4620	1.3970	-1.70	-116.2
7	3.00	59.00	41.00	1.7700	1.3970	-2.02	-114.1
8	3.50	59.50	40.50	2.0830	1.3970	-2.37	-113.8

The emulsions were prepared in 125 c.c. glass-stoppered bottles; 25 c.c. of the continuous phase were introduced in each bottle and the oil dispersed in it gradually by shaking in an electrically driven shaker, giving up and

down angular motion (similar to shaking with hand) with 6" stroke and 230 oscillations per minute.

After the required percentage content of the disperse phase was reached the emulsions were homogenised and freed from air-bubbles by placing the bottles in a water-bath at 45°. The clear emulsions were allowed to cool to room temperature before introducing them in the polarimeter observation tube. The optical rotations of the emulsions were found within 2 hours after preparation, as the lowest (28.57%) creamed after about 3 hours. The optical rotations for the emulsions were also calculated from the Beer's law for mixtures $B' = B/(n + 1)$. This law was tested practically by adding equal quantity of glycerine to 1.16% gelatin-water sol. The optical rotation at 26° for 1.16% gelatin-water sol is -1.37 and the optical rotation at 26° for 1.16% gelatin-water sol + glycerine (1:1) is -0.68, half of the above as required by the law. Emulsions of each concentration of gelatin were prepared thrice and studied independently for the optical rotation. The readings varied within 0.02. The mean of the three different readings were taken as final. The observed and calculated optical rotation of emulsions prepared in gelatin sols of various concentrations and the values of α/m , calculated from the difference of the two, are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Cont. phase No.	% content of disperse phase (v).	Rotation calc.	Rotation obs.	% of gelatin actual (d).	in emulsion calc. (c).	Gelatin adsorbed (d-c).	$\frac{\alpha}{m} = \frac{d-c}{\rho v}$
1	28.57 c.c.	-0.24	-0.16	0.1994 g.	0.1329 g.	0.0665 g.	0.000701
	37.50	-0.21	-0.12	0.1744	0.0997	0.0747	0.002311
	44.44	-0.19	-0.08	0.1579	0.0665	0.0914	0.002385
	50.00	-0.17	-0.03	0.1412	0.0249	0.1163	0.002699
2	28.57	-0.35	-0.23	0.3041	0.1920	0.1121	0.004552
	37.50	-0.32	-0.15	0.2661	0.1252	0.1409	0.004359
	44.44	-0.28	-0.09	0.2367	0.0751	0.1616	0.004709
	50.00	-0.26	-0.03	0.2128	0.0250	0.1878	0.004356
3	28.57	-0.48	-0.32	0.3967	0.2642	0.1325	0.005380
	37.50	-0.42	-0.18	0.3470	0.1487	0.1983	0.006135
	44.44	-0.37	-0.10	0.3058	0.0825	0.2233	0.005829
	50.00	-0.34	-0.05	0.2809	0.0413	0.2396	0.005559
4	28.57	-0.71	-0.55	0.6120	0.4741	0.1379	0.005601
	37.50	-0.62	-0.38	0.5388	0.3275	0.2113	0.006537
	44.44	-0.55	-0.27	0.4793	0.2328	0.2465	0.006434
	50.00	-0.50	-0.19	0.4310	0.1638	0.2672	0.006198

TABLE II (contd.).

5	28°57	-0.06	-0.79	0.8162	0.6688 g.	0.1474	0.005985
	37°50	-0.84	-0.58	0.7137	0.4910	0.2227	0.006892
	44°44	-0.75	-0.45	0.6351	0.3810	0.2541	0.006633
	50°00	-0.67	-0.34	0.5715	0.2878	0.2837	0.006583
6	28°57	-1.20	-1.02	1.0330	0.8778	0.1552	0.006302
	37°50	-1.05	-0.78	0.9036	0.6713	0.2323	0.007188
	44°44	-0.93	-0.52	0.8004	0.5315	0.2669	0.006968
	50°00	-0.84	-0.49	0.7230	0.4217	0.3013	0.006990
7	28°57	-1.43	-1.24	1.2510	1.0860	0.1650	0.006701
	37°50	-1.25	-0.98	1.0950	0.8588	0.2362	0.007305
	44°44	-1.11	-0.78	0.9727	0.6923	0.2804	0.007319
	50°00	-1.00	-0.64	0.8764	0.5610	0.3154	0.007318
8	28°57	-1.68	-1.47	1.4760	1.2910	0.1850	0.007513
	37°50	-1.47	-1.19	1.2010	1.0460	0.2450	0.007580
	44°44	-1.30	-0.98	1.1470	0.8610	0.2860	0.007466
	50°00	-1.17	-0.81	1.0320	0.7117	0.3203	0.007430

FIG. I.

The graphs showing the relation between the equilibrium concentration c (calculated from the observed rotations) and x/m , the quantity adsorbed by 1 g. of the disperse phase, are shown in Fig. 1.

Since it was found that the values of x/m were nearly constant with different quantities of the adsorbent by the above mentioned method, it was worth while to apply the same for measuring the adsorption of gelatin in milky emulsions of amyl acetate in gelatin-water sol.

The various quantities (10, 15, 20, 25 c.c.) of amyl acetate were added to 14.25 c.c. of 10% gelatin-water sol and four milky emulsions were obtained by first shaking with hand after every addition of 2 c.c. and then in the mechanical shaker. It was not possible to prepare these emulsions by directly shaking in the mechanical shaker, as the disperse phase separated immediately after the shaking was stopped.

To each of these milky emulsions, 10.75 c.c. of glycerine (dehydrated and having refractive index $n_D^{20} = 1.4700$) were added to make it transparent. After addition of glycerine, it was once more shaken in the mechanical shaker, and then homogenised, and freed from air-bubbles.

The observed optical rotations and the values of c , x , and x/m , calculated therefrom, are shown in Table III.

TABLE III.

Vol. of disperse phase.	Rotation calc.	Rotation obs.	% of gelatin actual d .	% of gelatin calc c .	Adsorbed gelatin $(d-c)=x$.	$\frac{x}{m}$.
28.57 c.c.	-0.48	-0.42	0.3967 g.	0.3468 g.	1.0499 g.	0.002026 g.
37.50	-0.42	-0.33	0.3470	0.2726	0.0744	0.002302
44.44	-0.37	-0.26	0.3058	0.2147	0.0911	0.002378
50.00	-0.34	-0.21	0.2809	0.1734	0.1075	0.002494

On comparing the results of Table III with those of emulsion No. 3 of Table I, it was observed that adsorption of gelatin from 1% gelatin-water sol was less than from 0.57% gelatin-water-glycerol sol. This was found to be due to the lower interfacial tension between the two phases in the latter case than in the former. As determined by the drop-pipette method, the interfacial tension in the former case was 8.134 and in the latter was 7.3940 dynes/cm. It is concluded from the above results that the quantity of gelatin adsorbed from 1% gelatin-water sol remains unaffected on addition of glycerine.

In order to investigate whether the gelatin in the adsorbed state becomes temporarily or permanently optically inactive, the stable 50% emulsions of amyl acetate in various gelatin-water-glycerol sols, were partially broken mechanically by adding 10 c.c. of amyl acetate (*i.e.* by overloading) and shaking the same in the mechanical shaker continuously for one hour, as suggested by Stirling (*J Inst. Petrol. Tech.*, 1920, 6, 382). The oil, thus separated, was measured and the optical rotation of the remaining emulsion was found out as shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

% Conc. of gelatin in cont. phase.	Amyl acetate separated (including extra 10 c.c.).	% Content of amyl acetate in the remaining emulsion.	Optical rotation of the remaining emulsion
0.2825 g.	35.00 c.c.	0.00	-0.34
0.4257	34.50	1.95	-0.46
0.5700	32.00	10.71	-0.48
0.8626	29.50	14.75	-0.67
1.1600	26.00	26.50	-0.82
1.4620	25.00	28.57	-1.02
1.7700	24.50	29.58	-1.19
2.0830	24.10	30.36	-1.38

On comparing the optical rotations of the remaining emulsions with those of the corresponding 50% emulsions, it is observed that in all cases, there is an increase in the optical rotation. In the case of 0.2825% gelatin sol, all the disperse phase is separated and the continuous phase remains behind; the optical rotation of this continuous phase is exactly the same as the original (compare Tables I & IV), *i.e.*, the gelatin in the original state has been recovered. Similarly in the case of 1.4620% gelatin sol, 28.57% emulsion remains behind; the optical rotation of this emulsion is the same as that given in Table II. From these experimental facts it is concluded that the gelatin films, optically inactive, become active on breaking. So there is a temporary loss of optical activity by gelatin particles adsorbed on the oil globules.

D I S C U S S I O N.

It is concluded from Table II that gelatin becomes optically inactive in the adsorbed state because the observed value of the optical rotation for a transparent emulsion is less than that calculated from Beer's law. This agrees well with the observation made by Bhatnagar and Shrivastava (*loc. cit.*) that sugars become optically inactive when adsorbed on colloidal particles. It is also observed that more and more quantity of gelatin is adsorbed as the quantity of the adsorbent (disperse phase) is increased.

Holmes and Child (*loc. cit.*) found out experimentally by creaming method that no gelatin is adsorbed on the oil globules and hence there are no protecting films round them. They attributed the stability of gelatin emulsions to the viscosity of the continuous phase. Narwani (*Kolloid Z.*, 1935, 70, 297) concluded from the study of the surface tension, viscosity, and ageing effect of emulsions of cod-liver oil in gelatin-glycerol sols, that gelatin films exist round the oil globules. The present work confirms quantitatively the adsorption of gelatin at the liquid/liquid interface and thus settles the long standing dispute over the existence of gelatin films round the oil globules.

It was not possible to prepare emulsions of higher percentage content of the oil than 50% by using continuous phases, containing less than 0.5% of gelatin. This fact is also confirmed by a very low optical rotation obtained from 50% emulsions, prepared in gelatin sols of lower concentrations.

The value of x/m (quantity of gelatin adsorbed by 1 g. of disperse phase) in case of various percentage contents of the disperse phase of an emulsion are fairly constant. The value of x/m goes on increasing with the increase in the initial concentration of gelatin. The curve showing the relation between c , the equilibrium concentration and x/m resembles that obtained by Briggs (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1915, 19, 210) for emulsions of benzene in sodium oleate solutions. He titrated 10 c.c. emulsion directly with $N/20$ -HCl, assuming that the adsorbed sodium oleate did not react with HCl. Hence our assumption that the gelatin becomes optically inactive on being adsorbed on oil globules, seems to hold good.

This loss of optical activity may be attributed either to orientation of gelatin molecules at the interface as suggested by Langmuir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 354, 541) or to catalytic condensation of the closely packed, specifically strained, and orientated protein molecules into a single vast chemical aggregate—activated amino- and carboxyl groups of neighbouring molecules uniting by peptide linkages with formation of water as suggested by Ramsden (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 22, 484). But since the optically inactive gelatin film again becomes active as concluded from the results shown in Table IV, the temporary orientation of the adsorbed molecules is more likely than their chemical condensation.

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